

Extraction studies of Zn^{II} from salicylate medium using Cyanex-923 extractant in toluene

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Manuscript received online 29 May 2014, revised 04 August 2014, accepted 07 August 2014

Abstract : Cyanex-923 extractant has been used for the extraction of Zn^{II} from sodium salicylate medium. This metal ion was quantitatively extracted with Cyanex-923 in toluene at pH 5 and from the organic phase it is stripped back with 1 M HCl solution. The effect of pH, sodium salicylate concentration, reagent concentration, equilibration period, diluents, diverse ions and stripping agent on the extraction of Zn^{II} has been studied. The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined on the basis of slope analysis method. The extraction proceed by solvation mechanism and the probable extracted species was Zn(HSal)₂.2Cyanex-923.

Keywords : Zn^{II}, Cyanex-923, toluene, multicomponent mixtures, nycil powder.

Introduction

Selective solvent extraction of transition metal ions like Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} was carried out from acidic aqueous media using benzimidazole-phosphinate¹. Cyanex reagents have been widely studied and employed for the extraction of Zn^{II}. The extraction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-272, Cyanex-302 and Cyanex-301 from nitrate, chloride and sulphate media have been studied by many worker²⁻⁷. Kinetic and mechanism of extraction of Zn^{II} is investigated by tributyl phosphates and triphenyl phosphite^{8,9}. Extraction of Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} was also performed with dialkyl thiophosphinic acid and hexadentate nitrogen donor ligand¹⁰. Recovery of Zn^{II} from HCl spent pickling solution is done by solvent extraction using Cyanex-921, Cyanex-923, Cyanex-303, tributyl phosphate and Alamines 336 extractant¹¹. Removal of Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} from crude phosphoric acid media was also studied by Cyanex-272¹². Methyl-2-(4-methoxybenzoyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-oxopropanoyl carbamate (MMPC) has been proposed as a new complexing agent for Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} ions using solvent extraction prior to their determination by flame atomic absorption spectrometry¹³. The present paper deals with the extraction of Zn^{II} from salicylate media using

Cyanex-923 in toluene.

Materials and methods :

Apparatus and reagents :

The extractant, Cyanex-923 supplied by Cytec Industries Inc., Canada was used without further purification. A known amount of zinc sulphate was dissolved and diluted with double distilled water as per requirement. All other chemical used were of analytical grade. EQUIP-TRONIC model EQ-614 pH meter with combined electrode was used for H⁺ ions concentration studies and ELICO UV-Visible SL-27 spectrophotometer with 10 mm cortex quartz cuvettes for absorbance measurements.

Procedure :

An aliquot containing 20 µg of Zn^{II} and 0.0025 M sodium salicylate in 10 ml was taken and equilibrated with equal volume of 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene for the required shaking time of 10 min, after adjusting their aqueous solution to pH 5.0 with dilute HCl and NH₃. The metal loaded organic phase was then stripped with 1 M HCl and was determined spectrophotometrically by the Murexide¹⁴ method at 460 nm. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH :

Extraction of Zn^{II} containing 0.0025 M sodium salicylate was carried out in the pH range of 1.0–7.0 with 0.01 M Cyanex-923 diluted in toluene. With the increase in pH the extraction goes on increasing and found to be quantitative at pH 5.0. Hence all the extraction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-923 was carried out at a fixed pH of 5.0.

Effect of Cyanex-923 concentration :

Extraction of Zn^{II} was also carried out by varying the reagent concentration from 0.001 to 0.1 M, while keeping other parameters like pH, period of equilibration, diluent and temperature constant. Extraction was found to increase with increase in reagent concentration. The distribution ratio increases with increases in the reagent concentration. The extraction of Zn^{II} was quantitative in the range 0.01 to 0.1 M Cyanex-923 in toluene, hence all the extractions of Zn^{II} were carried at fixed reagent concentration of 0.01 M.

Effect of sodium salicylate :

The effect of sodium salicylate concentration on the percentage extraction of Zn^{II} with 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene was studied in the sodium salicylate range from 0.00025 to 0.005 M. As the sodium salicylate concentration increases the extraction goes on increasing and becomes quantitative in the range 0.0025–0.005 M with Cyanex-923 in toluene. Hence all the extractions were carried out at 0.0025 M sodium salicylate with Cyanex-923.

Effect of diluents and period of equilibration :

Various aromatic and aliphatic diluents like toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, cyclohexane, *n*-hexane and xylene were employed for extraction of Zn^{II} . The extraction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-923 was found to be quantitative with toluene, *n*-hexane and carbon tetrachloride. Toluene was used as best diluent for Cyanex-923 extractant because of quick and better phase separation (Table 1). Extraction equilibrium was studied for different periods of shaking, ranging from 1–30 min. It was observed that 10 min of shaking period was sufficient for quantita-

Table 1. Effect of diluents on percentage extraction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-923

Diluents	Cyanex-923	
	Percentage extraction	Distribution ratio
	(%E)	(D)
<i>n</i> -Hexane	99.9	999
Toluene	99.9	999
Xylene	93.1	13.58
Cyclohexane	86.7	6.52
Carbon tetrachloride	99.9	999
Chloroform	67.7	2.10

tive extraction of Zn^{II} with 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene. However there was no adverse effect by increasing the extraction period upto 30 min.

Effect of various stripping agents :

Zn^{II} was stripped out from its metal loaded organic phases with different strength of mineral acids like HCl, HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 . It was found that quantitative stripping of Zn^{II} from the organic phase was observed with 1 M HCl and 4 M HNO_3 (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of stripping agents on percentage recovery of Zn^{II} from metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 in toluene

Acids	Percentage recovery (%R) of Zn^{II} from metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 in toluene, with strippants		
	HCl	H_2SO_4	HNO_3
Molarity (mol/dm ³)			
1.0	99.9	35.5	21.5
2.0	97.3	56.0	44.8
3.0	68.1	68.9	87.9
4.0	60.0	85.4	99.9

Stoichiometry of extracted species :

It was necessary to evaluate the distribution coefficient (*D*) while varying the extractant concentration to ascertain the nature of extracted species. The composition of the extracted species was first ascertained from graph of log *D* versus log *R* at fixed pH of 5.0. The slope obtained was 2.0, indicating that two molecules of Cyanex-

923 react with one molecule of zinc ion. The slope of log *D* versus log [HSal⁻] is also 2.0, suggesting that two molecules of salicylate ion are used up in the process. The probable compositions of the extractable species of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-923 is 1 : 2 and the probable extracted species is Zn(HSal)₂.2Cyanex-923 which is similar to the earlier reported with triphenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO)¹⁵. The extraction of metal ion thus involves solvation of metal salicylate molecule. The probable extraction mechanism¹⁶ could be expressed as follows,

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of various diverse ions on the extraction of Zn^{II} was studied with Cyanex-923 in toluene. The tolerance limit of individual foreign ions was set so that error in percentage recovery was not more than $\pm 2\%$. It was found that EDTA highly interfered while alkali metal like Na^I, Li^I, K^I, Cs^{II} are highly tolerated (1 : 48). The other ions like Cl⁻, Br⁻, SO₄²⁻, I⁻, S²⁻ and ClO₄⁻ interfered in the ratio 1 : 39, Mn^{II}, V^V, Cr^{III}, Ni^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II} and Pb^{II} in the ratio 1 : 22, Ti^{IV}, Cd^{II} and Rb^I in the ratio 1 : 9 and Ga^{III}, Be^{II}, Al^{III} and Ti^{III} in the ratio 1 : 4.

Influence of temperature :

Extraction of Zn^{II} with 0.01 *M* Cyanex-923 in toluene at a fixed sodium salicylate concentration of 0.0025 *M* and at fix pH of 3.0 were carried out at different temperatures (upto 343 K). The distribution ratio decreased with an increase in temperature. As per the Van't Hoff equation of $\log D_{\text{Zn}} = -(\Delta H/2.303 RT) + C$, where *D*_{Zn} represent the distribution ratio, ΔH is the enthalpy change for the reaction and *C* is the constant. The slopes obtained from the linear plot of log *D*_{Zn} vs 1000/*T* was 1.39. The ΔH values calculated was -26.61 kJ mol⁻¹ indicating that the extraction reaction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-923 is exothermic in nature.

Separation of Zn^{II} from multicomponent mixtures :

Zn^{II} was separated from various metals ions by ex-

ploring the difference in their extraction conditions. The mixtures containing Zn^{II}, Ti^{III}, Ti^{IV} and Fe^{III} was resolved by first adjusting the pH of the solution at 1.5 using 0.005 *M* Cyanex-923 in toluene when Ti^{III} was extracted in the organic phase while Zn^{II}, Ti^{IV} and Fe^{III} remained unextracted in the aqueous phase. From the organic phase Ti^{III} was stripped with 3.0 *M* HCl and determined by PAR method¹⁷. Zn^{II}, Ti^{IV} and Fe^{III} which were not extracted and remained in the aqueous phase were separated first by extracting Zn^{II} with 0.0025 *M* sodium salicylate and 0.01 *M* Cyanex-923 at pH 5.0, when Ti^{IV} and Fe^{III} remained unextracted in the aqueous phase. Extracted Zn^{II} was then stripped with 1.0 *M* HCl. Ti^{IV} and Fe^{III} were separated by extracting Fe^{III} at 6.0 *M* HCl with 0.005 *M* Cyanex-923 while Ti^{IV} remained unextracted. Fe^{III} was the stripped from the organic phase with water and determined by thiocyanate method¹⁸ while unextracted Ti^{IV} is determined by H₂O₂ method¹⁹.

A ternary mixture containing Zn^{II}, Be^{II} and Fe^{III} was resolved by first equilibrating their solution containing 0.0025 *M* sodium salicylate at pH 5.0, with 0.01 *M* of Cyanex-923 diluted in toluene for about 5 min during which only Zn^{II} was extracted in the organic phase which was then stripped with 1.0 *M* HCl. While aqueous solution containing unextracted Be^{II} and Fe^{III} was further equilibrated with 0.01 *M* Cyanex-923 at pH 8.0, whereby only Be^{II} was extracted with Cyanex-923 and Fe^{III} remained unextracted in the aqueous solution. The Be^{II} from the organic phase was stripped with 0.5 *M* NaOH. The amount of Be^{II} and Fe^{III} was determined with quinalizarin²⁰ and thiocyanate method.

Similarly Zn^{II} was separated from other metal ions easily which are summarised in Table 3. The metal ions like Al^{III} and Ga^{III} are determined by Aluminon²¹ and PAR method respectively.

Analysis of pharmaceutical sample :

Nycil (talc powder) : The sample (20–25 mg) was treated with the minimum necessary amount of concentrated sulphuric acid, the solution was diluted a little with water, filter to remove the white residue, then diluted to about 25 ml and analysed for zinc¹⁵.

Table 3. Separation of Zn^{II} from multicomponent mixtures with Cyanex-923 in toluene

Sr. No.	Mixtures	Amount taken (μg)	pH/ Acidity	Extractant Cyanex-923	Stripping agents	Percentage recovery (%R)
1.	Tl ^{III}	50	1.5	0.005 M	3.0 M HCl	99.4
	Zn ^{II}	20	0.0025 M NaSaly. (pH = 5)	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.3
2.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M HCl	0.005 M	Water	99.5
	Ti ^{IV}	50	6.0 M HCl	0.005 M	Unextracted	99.2
	Zn ^{II}	20	0.0025 M NaSaly. (pH = 5)	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.5
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.6
3.	Fe ^{III}	50	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.4
	Zn ^{II}	20	0.0025 M NaSaly. (pH = 5)	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.2
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.2
	Cu ^{II}	20	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.1
4.	Al ^{III}	15	5.0	0.005 M	1.0 M HCl	99.5
	Zn ^{II}	20	0.0025 M NaSaly. (pH = 5)	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.2
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.4
	Cu ^{II}	20	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.3
5.	Ga ^{III}	5	4.5	0.005 M	4.0 M HNO ₃	99.5
	Zn ^{II}	20	0.0025 M NaSaly. (pH = 5)	0.01 M	1.0 M HCl	99.2
	Be ^{II}	15	8.0	0.01 M	0.5 M NaOH	99.4
	Fe ^{III}	50	8.0	0.01 M	Unextracted	99.2

The results were in good agreement with certified value and those of an independent analysis (Table 4).

Table 4. Analysis of pharmaceutical sample

Sample	Manufactured by	Amount of zinc certified	Amount found by proposed method ^a	R.S.D.
Nycil (Prickly heat powder)	Glaxo Laboratories (India) Ltd. (Glindia Ltd.)	12.8%	12.7%	0.48

^aAverage of triplicate analysis.

Conclusion

- (i) The results obtained indicate that Zn^{II} can be quantitatively extracted with Cyanex-923 dissolved in toluene at pH 5.0 in presence of 0.0025 M sodium salicylate.

- (ii) The ΔH value evaluated with extractant Cyanex-923 is $-26.61 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ indicating that extraction reaction is exothermic in nature.
- (iii) The concentration of reagents required for the extraction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-923 (0.01 M) is less compared to acidic organophosphorous extractants like Cyanex-272, Cyanex-302 and Cyanex-301 in Exxsol D-80 which required 0.6 M.
- (iv) The extraction of Zn^{II} with Cyanex-301 extractants in acidic media showed only 85% and 80% extraction⁴, while poor extraction is observed with diethyl dithiocarbamate²². However quantitative extraction of zinc(II) is observed with Cyanex-923 in toluene.
- (v) The proposed method is applied for the analysis of Zn^{II} in pharmaceutical sample.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Cytec Industries Inc., Canada for supplying Cyanex-923 as gift sample.

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